

STUDIES ON SEED-BORNE MYCOFLORA OF PEARL MILLET (*Pennisetum typhoides*) AND THEIR MANAGEMENT THROUGH BOTANICALSK. M. Bhelave^{1*}, Dr. S. W. Khodake², Dr. S. T. Ingle³ and V. P. Dhanorkar⁴¹M.Sc. Scholar, Department of Plant Pathology, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, India.²Professor, Department of Plant Pathology, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, Maharashtra.³Professor, Department of Plant Pathology, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, India⁴M.Sc. Scholar, Department of Plant Pathology, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, Maharashtra.kartikbhelave001@gmail.com

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Abstract

Fungi associated with pearl millet (*Pennisetum typhoides*) seeds pose serious threats to plant health and indirectly, to human health by impacting seed germination and seedling growth. This study identifies five main fungal pathogens *Alternaria alternata*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Fusarium moniliforme* and *Rhizoctonia solani* that are prevalent on pearl millet seeds. Four cultivars of pearl millets were collected and tested for the detection and identification of seed-borne mycoflora by Standard blotter paper method. Five botanicals were evaluated against the seed-borne mycoflora of pearl millet. Among the botanicals tested, the mean maximum growth inhibition of major seed-borne mycoflora was observed in Garlic (74.70% and 85.43%) at concentrations of 5% and 10% respectively. Followed by Datura (69.53% and 76.84%), Neem (50.10% and 63.92%), Tulsi (40.91% and 56.20%) and the least inhibition was observed in Aloe Vera (42.86% and 51.48%) at 5% and 10% concentration respectively.

Keywords: Pearl millet, seed-borne mycoflora, Detection, Inhibition

Introduction

Pearl millet (*Pennisetum typhoides*), the fourth most significant cereal crop in India after rice, wheat and maize, plays a crucial role in feeding millions in arid regions. Indigenous to Africa and the Indian subcontinent, it thrives in extreme drought-prone conditions where other crops falter. Globally, it is cultivated over approximately 31 million hectares, with India leading in production and area covered, particularly in states such as Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Gujarat, Haryana, Karnataka, Maharashtra and Andhra Pradesh. In India, pearl millet is grown on 6.70 m hectares with production of 9.62 m tonnes annually, with Rajasthan contributing the largest share (Anonymous, 2022).

Despite its resilience and nutritional benefits providing essential carbohydrates, proteins, vitamins and minerals pearl millet faces significant threats from seed-borne mycoflora. These fungi, including *Alternaria alternata*, *Fusarium moniliforme*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Curvularia lunata*, etc., negatively impact seed germination, seedling vigour and overall plant health (Faso, 2008). They can also produce mycotoxins harmful to humans and animals. Seed-borne pathogens not only reduce germination rates and seed quality but also lead to severe yield losses, with potential reductions in crop productivity ranging from 10-40% depending on infection severity and environmental conditions (Rathore and Shekhawat, 2002).

The management of these pathogens is critical for maintaining seed quality and ensuring high crop yields. The *in vitro* efficacy of botanicals against seed-borne mycoflora in pearl millet is crucial for sustainable disease management. It provides an eco-friendly alternative to chemical fungicides, reducing harmful environmental impacts while preserving seed health, germination and crop yield. By minimizing chemical residues in food and preventing post-harvest losses caused by fungal infections, botanicals offer a cost-effective and accessible solution for farmers. Additionally, their use helps prevent the development of resistant fungal strains and supports organic farming practices, contributing to integrated pest management (IPM) and the development of biopesticides. Keeping in view the research was carried out using different botanicals against *Alternaria alternata*, *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Fusarium moniliforme*. During this investigation, various experiments were conducted at the Department of Plant Pathology, Post graduate institute, Dr. PDKV., Akola (Maharashtra), during 2023-24.

Materials And Methods**Collection of seed samples**

This study was carried out on four cultivars of pearl millet including Mahabeej-1005, AHB 1200 FE, Dhanashakti and Phule Adishakti, which were collected from Department of Seed Technology, Dr. PDKV

Akola and Mahabeej Quality Control Laboratory in Shioni, Akola (Maharashtra).

Detection of seed-borne mycoflora of Pearl millet by different methods

Seeds were examined for seed-borne mycoflora by using standard blotter paper method (ISTA, 1996).

Standard blotter paper method

Sterilized blotter paper discs of 90 mm diameter were placed in sterile Petri plates (90 mm dia.) and moistened with sterile distilled water. The excess water was drained off from the plates. Four hundred seeds of pearl millet cultivars were transferred to the plates containing the moist blotter paper. In each plate, 25 seeds were placed in such a manner as 16 seeds in outer ring, 8 seeds in inner ring and 1 seed at the center. Four hundred seeds from each sample were placed in the plates in four replications. The plates were incubated at 25 ± 2°C under 12 h alternating cycles of light and darkness for 7-10 days. The plates were examined under the stereo binocular microscope on the 7th day and a total number of fungal colonies was counted and expressed in percentage (Neergaard, 1979 and Nelson *et al.*, 1983).

The frequency of occurrence of seed-borne pathogens on the seeds in all the above-mentioned methods was calculated by the following formula.

$$\text{Frequency of occurrence (\%)} = \frac{\text{Number of seeds infected}}{\text{Total number of seeds evaluated}} \times 100$$

Isolation and purification of seed-borne mycoflora

As soon as fungal colonies were observed on the seeds of pearl millet varieties, plates were transferred aseptically on potato dextrose agar (PDA) slants with the help of a sterilized inoculating needle under controlled conditions. The isolates obtained were then maintained in pure form on potato dextrose agar slants, numbered carefully and preserved at a low temperature in the refrigerator for further studies (Bhale *et al.*, 2001).

Identification of seed-borne mycoflora

The identification of fungi was done based on morphology and colony characters, fruiting body, conidiophores and conidia with the help of published literature.

In vitro bioefficacy of plant extracts/botanicals

The plant leaves extract were prepared by adopting the aqueous extracting method. The standard aqueous leaf extract of the selected botanicals (Table 1) was obtained by grinding the washed plant leaves (100 g) in mortar and pestle in presence of equal amount of sterilized distilled water (100 ml). Prepared leaves extract were filtered through folds of muslin cloth, make up the volume and treated as 100% extract. These filtered extracts were autoclaved at 1.2 kg cm⁻¹ pressure for 20 minutes. The autoclaved extract was individually added into

previously sterilized PDA at 5 and 10 per cent concentrations and mixed thoroughly at the time of pouring in the previously sterilized Petri plates. After solidification of the PDA medium, all the plates were inoculated aseptically by placing in the center a 5 mm culture disc obtained from actively growing 7 days pure culture of seed-borne fungi and incubated in an inverted position at $25 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$. Petri plates filled with plain PDA (without phytoextract) and inoculated with the pure cultures were maintained as untreated control. The growth inhibition

percent was recorded in different poisoned media by using the following formula (Vincent, 1947).

$$\text{Per cent growth inhibition} = \frac{C - T}{C} \times 100$$

Where,

C = Growth (mm) of the pathogen in untreated control plates.

T = Growth (mm) of the pathogen in treated plates.

Table 1. List botanicals used against seed borne mycoflora of pearl millet

Sr. No.	Botanicals	Botanical name	Plant Part Used	Conc. (%)
T ₁	Aloe Vera	<i>Aloe barbadensis</i>	Leaves	5 and 10
T ₂	Garlic	<i>Allium sativum</i>	Clove	5 and 10
T ₃	Tulsi	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	Leaves	5 and 10
T ₄	Neem	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Leaves	5 and 10
T ₅	Dhatura	<i>Datura stramonium</i>	Leaves	5 and 10
T ₆	Control	-	-	-

Results And Discussion

Detection of seed-borne mycoflora of Pearl millet

In the present investigation entitled "Studies on seed-borne mycoflora of Pearl millet (*Pennisetum typhoides*) and their Management through botanicals" seed-borne mycoflora were associated with different varieties of pearl millet and their management with botanicals were studied and the results of the study are presented and discussed as under.

Standard blotter paper method

The data pertaining to estimation of seed mycoflora of pearl millet analyzed through standard blotter method is presented in Table 2.

Five seed-borne mycoflora, belonging to different genera including both saprophytic and pathogenic types, were recorded. The mycoflora observed and identified as *Fusarium moniliforme* (23.39%), *Aspergillus flavus* (21.79%), *Rhizoctonia solani* (21.47%), *Alternaria alternata* (19.23%) and *Aspergillus niger* (14.10%). Discussion

warranted in respect to less or maximum association of mycoflora in respective cultivars the maximum frequency of seed-borne mycoflora was recorded on Dhanashakti (26.92%), followed by AHB 1200 FE (26.60%), Phule adishakti (26.28%) and Mahabeej-1005 (20.19%)

These findings of different authors confirmative to results of the present investigation though they have tested the different crop seeds under varied type of geographical climatic conditions. Fakhrunnisa et al. (2006) identified standard blotter and deep-freezing methods for the detection of seed-borne mycoflora of wheat, sorghum and barley. Fungi most frequently isolated and identified were *Alternaria alternata*, *Aspergillus* spp., *A. flavus*, *A. niger*, *Curvularia lunata*, *Drechslera* spp., *Fusarium moniliforme*, *F. oxysporum* and *Penicillium* spp. Khairnar et al. (2011) studied biodiversity in seed of some cereals of Nashik district, 27 fungal species were found in association with six cereal and maximum fungi was reported from seeds of pearl millet and sorghum.

Table 2. Association of seed-borne mycoflora with pearl millet (Standard blotter paper method)

Sr. No.	Cultivars	Frequency of seed-borne mycoflora					Total association (%)
		<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>	<i>Fusarium moniliforme</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	
1	Phule Adishakti	5.44	5.12	6.08	3.52	6.08	26.28
2	Dhanashakti	4.80	6.41	6.73	3.20	5.76	26.92
3	AHB 1200 FE	5.12	6.73	6.73	3.84	4.16	26.60
4	Mahabeej 1005	3.84	3.20	3.84	3.52	5.76	20.19
	Total Fungi (%)	19.23	21.47	23.39	14.10	21.79	78.00

In vitro bioefficacy of plant extracts/botanicals

After assessing the association of seed-borne mycoflora in pearl millet, evaluating the efficacy of botanicals against the highest associated and pathogenic seed mycoflora only. Seed-borne fungi like *Alternaria alternata*, *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Fusarium moniliforme* can significantly affect seed health, reducing germination and crop yield.1) Botanicals offer a natural, eco-friendly alternative to chemical2) treatments. *In vitro* studies help identify effective plant extracts that inhibit or eliminate these pathogens, minimizing the need for synthetic fungicides. This ensures improved seed quality, better germination rates, and overall plant health, while also reducing environmental impact and post-harvest losses.

Aqueous extracts of five botanicals viz., Aloe Vera, Garlic, Tulsi, Neem and Dhatura were evaluated *in vitro* (each @ 5 and 10%) against *Alternaria alternata*, *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Fusarium moniliforme*. The results obtained on its mycelial growth and inhibition were presented in Table 3, Figure 1 & 2 and Plate 1.

Alternaria alternata

The data presented in Table 3 indicated that the maximum (87.26% and 100%) growth inhibition of *Alternaria alternata* was observed in Garlic, at all concentrations (5% and 10%) respectively followed by Dhatura, (68.04% and 78.02%), Aloe Vera (62.38% and 73.43%), and Tulsi (55.96% and 77.27%) The least inhibition was observed in Neem (53.72% and 67.94%) respectively.

These results are in conformity with Chaudhary and Singh (2021) evaluated different botanicals against *Alternaria* leaf spot of ber. Total nine different botanicals *i.e.* Neem, Garlic, Parthenium, Tulsi, Dhatura, Turmeric, Ginger, Onion, Eucalyptus were tested against *A. alternata* infection in ber leaves. All the botanicals were tested at 10%, 15% and 20% concentration, out of which Garlic (74.88%) showed maximum mycelium growth inhibition followed by ginger (73.51%) and Neem (69.25%). Misra and Dixit (1976) reported that garlic could be used as a potent fungicide against *A. alternata*, *C. lunata* plant pathogens *in vitro*. Yadav et al. (2019) investigated *Alternaria* blight caused *Alternaria brassicae* (Berk.) Sacc. Extracts of 29 plants was tested against their efficacy at 5% and 10% concentration (*in-vitro*). All the botanicals tested were effective showing different levels of concentration. All the 29 botanicals test extracts inhibited the spore germination of the pathogens. Garlic and Eucalyptus was most fungi toxic causing 100% inhibition at 5% and 10% concentration followed by Ashok (90.77% and 100%), Tulsi (87.44% and 100%), Dhatura (85.09% and 100%), Neem (82.44% and 100%), respectively.

Rhizoctonia solani

The data presented in Table 3 indicated that the maximum (70.30% and 77.88%) growth inhibition of *Rhizoctonia solani* was observed in Dhatura at all concentrations (5% and 10%) respectively followed by, Garlic (60.43% and 71.33%), Tulsi (21.28% and 37.46%), and Neem (12.30% and 36.58%) The least inhibition was observed in Aloe Vera (15.73% and 23.77%).

These results are in conformity with Yadav et al. (2021) investigate the antifungal efficacy of botanicals against sheath blight, caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* viz., Neem, Tulsi, Garlic, Onion and Ginger *in vitro* by poison food technique at 5 and 10 per cent concentrations. The bulb extract of garlic and ginger rhizome extract of ginger suppressed the mycelial growth (68.70 and 67.77 respectively) at 10%, and bulb extract of onion (63.52%) at 8 days after inoculation. Usha Rani et al. (2009) evaluated the bio efficacy of plant extracts against *Rhizoctonia solani*. Results revealed the growth inhibition in *Allium sativum* (86.6%) followed by *Polyalthia longiflora* (72.9%) and *Azadirachta indica* (48.7%). Gupta et al. (2020) evaluated the efficacy of different botanicals on the mycelial growth of *Rhizoctonia solani* at two concentrations of 10% and 20% the maximum per cent inhibition in growth was recorded by Garlic and Dhatura extracts.

3) Fusarium moniliforme

The data presented in Table 3 indicated that the maximum (83.61% and 86.66%) growth inhibition of *Fusarium moniliforme* was observed in Neem, at all concentrations (5% and 10%) respectively followed by Garlic, (76.39% and 84.95%), Dhatura (70.23% and 73.96%), and Aloe vera (50.45% and 57.36%) The least inhibition was observed in Tulsi (45.06% and 53.59%) respectively.

These results are in conformity with Singh et al. (2021) evaluated *in-vitro* studies to check effect of botanicals against *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *ciceri*. It was observed that the treatment with Neem leaves (*Azadirachta indica*) was found to be most effective against *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *Ciceri* showing minimum disease incidence followed by Guava leaf extract. It was observed that Neem leaves (*Azadirachta indica*) treatment was significantly superior as compared to other botanicals followed by Garlic, Dhatura and Tulsi. Abdel-Rahim et al. (2011) evaluated leaves sap of Aloe vera at 10% concentration is found to be most effective for control seed-borne fungi viz., *Aspergillus flavus*, *Penicillium oxalicum*, *Fusarium subglutinans*, *F. moniliforme*, and *F. verticillioides* isolated from corn, popcorn, and sorghum grains. Rathod and Pawar (2012) evaluated *in vitro* leaf extracts of *Azadirachta indica*, *Datura stramonium*, *Polyalthia longifolia*, *Allium sativum* and *Annona squamosa*. Reported *Datura stramonium* and *Azadirachta indica* extracts as the most effective.

Conclusions

All four cultivars of pearl millet, namely Mahabeej-1005, AHB 1200 FE, Dhanashakti and Phule Adishakti, were found to be associated with

seed-borne mycoflora. The standard blotter paper method was found to be the most effective for detecting seed-borne mycoflora of pearl millet, while the other methods were less effective. Among botanicals tested, Garlic bulb extracts were found effective against seed-borne mycoflora of pearl millet.

References

1. **Abdel-Rahim, M. A., El-Samawaty, Yassin, M. A., Bahkali, A., Moslem, M. and Abd-Elslam, K. A. (2011).** Bio-fungicidal activity of Aloe vera sap against mycotoxigenic seed-borne fungi. *Fresenius Environmental Bulletin*, 20(6): 1352-1359.
2. **Anonymous. (2022).** Agriculture at a glance (PP. 38-39). Agricultural-Statistics-at-a-glance-2022.pdf (desagri.gov.in).
3. **Bhale, M. S., Khare, D., Rawt, N. D. and Singh, D. (2001).** Seed-borne diseases objectionable in seed production and their management. Scientific Publishers, Jodhpur (India). pp: 10-16.
4. **Chaudhary S, Singh HK (2021)** *In-vitro* evaluation of different botanicals against *Alternaria alternata* causing *Alternaria* leaf spot of ber (*Ziziphus mauritiana* Lamk.). *Int J Econ Pl* 8 (1): 040-044.
5. **Fakhrunnisa M., H. Hashmi and A. Ghaffar, (2006).** Seed-borne mycoflora of wheat, sorghum and barley, *Pak. J. Bot*, 38(1): 185-192.
6. **Faso B. (2008)** Importance of seed-borne fungi of sorghum and pearl millet and their control. *PJBS* 11(3):321 331
7. **Khairnar, D.N., A.S. Kelhe, and A.B. Khaimar, (2011).** Fungal biodiversity in seeds of some cereals of Nashik District, and its pathogenicity and control measures. *Int. Res. J. of Science & Engineering*, 4 (1): 273-275.
8. **Khare M.N., (1996).** Methods to test seeds for associated fungi. *Indian Phytopathology*, 49 (4):319-328.
9. **Misra S. B. and S. N. Dixit, (1976).** Fungicidal spectrum of leaf extracts of *Allium sativum*. *Indian Phytopath*, 29: 448-448.
10. **Neergaard P., (1979).** Detection of seed-borne pathogen by culture test. *Seed Sci. & Tech*, 1: 217-254.
11. **Nelson P. E., T. A. Toussoun and W.F.O. Marasas, (1983).** *Fusarium* species. An Illustrated Manual of Identification. The Pennsylvania State Univ. Press, Univ. Park, Pennsylvania. pp 203.
12. **Rathod L. R. and P. V. Pawar, (2012).** Antimicrobial activity of medicinal plant to control seed-borne pathogen of soybean. *Current Botany* 2012, 3(2): 10-12 ISSN 2220-4822.
13. **Rathore, R. S., & Shekhawat, K. S. (2002).** Impact of seed-borne mycoflora on the yield and quality of pearl millet. *Plant Disease Research*, 17(2), 230-234.
14. **ISTA (1996)** International Rules for Seed Testing. *Seed Science and Technology*, 13, 299-513.
15. **Usha rani, S., Udaykumar, R. and D. John Christopher, (2009).** Bio-efficacy of plant extracts and bio-control agents against *Rhizoctonia solani* Ann. *Pl. Prot. Sci.*, 17 (1): 389-393.
16. **Verma, Babli & Gupta, Ashish & Fatehpuria, Pramod. (2020).** Evaluation of botanicals against growth of *Rhizoctonia solani* under *in vitro* condition. *International Journal of Chemical Studies*. 8.2781-2784. 10.22271.
17. **Vincent, J.M. 1947.** Distortion of fungal hyphae in the presence of certain inhibitors. 159-180.
18. **Yadav, V. K., Choudhary, V. P., Singh, S. K., Kumar, M., Maurya, S. P., Prasad, R., & Singh, A. (2021).** *In vitro* efficacy of botanicals against *Rhizoctonia solani* Kühn inciting sheath blight of rice.